

Comparative Study of the Influence of Series Resistance on the Magnitude and Peak Potential of A.C. Polarographic Peaks at the D.M.E.

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The effect of series resistance on the magnitudes and peak potentials of a.c. polarographic peaks has been studied. Tensammetric and reduction peaks of organic compounds are much less dependent on external series resistance than the a.c. reduction peaks of inorganic cations. The magnitudes of a.c. reduction peaks of inorganic cations depend on the dimension of the electrolysis cell and the distance of the d.m.e. from mercury pool anode, whereas organic reduction peak and tensammetric peak are influenced to a very less extent.

Breyer *et al.*¹ have shown that the maximum differential current ' $i_{D_{max}}$ ' obtained in the reduction of metal ions (Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}) increases on decreasing the ohmic resistance of the cell circuit. They further showed that the magnitude of such peaks also varied with the capillary distance from the mercury pool anode. Bauer and Elving² described an experimental procedure involving adequate corrections for the effect of the series resistances in the circuit and the data obtained on the reduction at the d.m.e. of $Cd(II)$ in hydrochloric acid solution were used to calculate the heterogeneous rate constant.

As no data are available in the literature regarding the effect of series resistance on the magnitudes and peak potentials of organic reduction peaks and tensammetric peaks, the present investigation has been undertaken to make comparative study of the influence of external and cell resistance on the magnitudes and peak potentials of a.c. polarographic peaks at the dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.).

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromothymol blue was of B.D.H. indicator quality. Cerfak and cetylpyridinium bromide were commercial detergents. Organic solid compounds used were either of B.D.H. or Merck's quality and were recrystallised before use. Organic liquid substances were also pure samples of either Merck or B.D.H. and were redistilled in all-glass fractionating column and middle one-thirds of the distillates were used for experiments. Other inorganic chemicals were of AnalaR quality of B.D.H. Mercury used for dropping electrode was purified as mentioned earlier³.

The experimental set-up and technique of measurement were the same as described before³. The d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the mercury pool

1. *Austri. J. Sci.*, 1950, 3, 567.

2. *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 30, 334.

3. *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 663.

anode and all the experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. The d.m.e. was cathodic throughout the measurements and its constants were: $m=4.564$ mg./sec.; $t=1.8$ sec. per drop in $0.1M$ -KCl, open circuit.

For the effect of cell resistance, the polarographic cell consisted of a glass tube of 1.5 cm in diameter, sealed at the bottom and provided with a "cap" drilled to accommodate d.m.e. A mercury pool on the bottom of the cell served as a reference electrode. Electrical contact with the pool electrode was brought about through the platinum wire, sealed in the bottom of the cell. The cell resistance was varied by changing the distance of the dropping electrode from the mercury pool anode. Resistance measurements were made using conductivity meter, type LBR of Wissenschaftlich-Technische, Workstätten, Germany. Carbon resistances were used to increase the series resistance in the cell circuit.

TABLE I
50 o/s A.C. ripple of ± 40 mV(r.m.s.). $pH = 11.2$. Conc. of indiff. electrolyte (KCl) = $0.1M$.

Substances.	Conc.	*	Cell resistance, Ω			
			0.5×10^3 .	0.9×10^3 .	1.2×10^3 .	1.6×10^3 .
A. Tensammetric peaks.						
n-Amyl alcohol	1.0%	A	210	210	208	200
		B	-1.22	-1.22	-1.23	-1.23
o-Cresol	1.0%	A	210	210	208	200
		B	-1.3	-1.3	-1.3	-1.3
Resorcinol	0.8%	A	76	76	76	76
		B	-1.14	-1.14	-1.14	-1.14
Phloroglucinol	0.6%	A	98	98	98	98
		B	-0.86	-0.86	-0.87	-0.88
Pyridine	1.0%	A	300	300	290	275
		B	-1.46	-1.47	-1.47	-1.48
Benzoic acid	$1.6 \times 10^{-3}M$	A	69	69	69	69
		B	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08
Camphor	0.08%	A	173	173	168	160
		B	-1.26	-1.26	-1.28	-1.28
Ether	6.0%	A	295	295	285	270
		B	-1.42	-1.42	-1.43	-1.44
Benzene	Satd.	A	193	193	190	181
		B	-1.02	-1.02	-1.02	-1.03
Aniline	0.06M	A	90	86	84	82
		B	-1.25	-1.25	-1.25	-1.25
Bromothymol blue	0.012%	A	210	209	—	207
		B	-1.0	-1.01	—	-1.01
Cetylpyridinium bromide	0.1%	A	86	81	79	77
		B	-1.27	-1.27	-1.28	-1.28

TABLE I (contd.)

Substances.	Conc.		Cell resistance, Ω			
			0.5×10^3 .	0.9×10^3 .	1.2×10^3 .	1.8×10^3 .
B. Organic reduction peaks.						
Nitrobenzene	$8 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	225	170	135	112
		B	-0.73	-0.74	-0.76	-0.76
o-Nitrophenol	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	50	48	42	37
		B	-0.73	-0.74	-0.75	-0.76
m-Nitrobenzoic acid	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	170	162	142	132
		B	-0.66	-0.69	-0.69	-0.71
3, 5-Dinitrobenzoic acid	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	102	159	142	128
		B	-0.66	-0.66	-0.68	-0.68
p-Nitroaniline	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	70	..	66	54
		B	-0.85	..	-0.88	-0.87
Benzaldehyde (pH 3.8)	$2 \times 10^{-3} M$	A	167	159	160	142
		B	-1.20	-1.20	-1.22	-1.24
C. Inorganic reduction peaks.						
Cd ²⁺ (pH 3.8)	$10^{-3} M$	A	800	585	427	361
		B	-0.62	-0.62	-0.63	-0.64
Zn ²⁺ (pH 3.8)	$10^{-3} M$	A	655	542	447	375
		B	-1.00	-1.01	-1.02	-1.02

*A denotes peak potential in volts and B, % increase in a.o.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Series Resistance to the Cell Circuit.—Fig. 1 shows the effect of series resistance on the magnitudes of the a.c. peaks. Curve 1 refers to the tensammetric peak, curve 2, to the a.c. reduction peak of organic compound, and curve 3, to the a.c. reduction peak of metal ion. The magnitudes of all the peaks decrease with increase in series resistance and follows the order: reduction peak due to metal ion > reduction peak due to organic compound > tensammetric peak. There is a small and similar shift in peak potential to more cathodic value with increase in series resistance for all the cases studied.

Effect of Cell Resistance.—The magnitude of a.c. reduction peaks of metal ions is noted to vary with the dimension of the electrolysis cell and especially with changes in the distance between the d.m.e. and the mercury pool reference electrode. The effect of increasing this distance was found to be qualitatively equivalent to the introduction of an external resistance into the cell circuit. Table I records the results obtained on such studies along with the effect on the magnitudes of tensammetric and organic reduction peaks. Here it can be seen that the effect is more prominent with the a.c. reduction peaks of metal ions and is much less with a.c. reduction peaks of organic compounds and tensammetric peaks. The reason for very small change in the magnitudes of tensammetric peak and reduction peak of organic compounds

is due to the limitations in the variation of the cell resistance. The peak potential also shifts slightly to more negative value with increase in the cell resistance. This further shows that tensammetric peaks and reduction peaks of organic compounds are much less dependent on the external resistance than the a. c. reduction peaks of inorganic cations. Incidentally, whatever effects on the magnitude of such peaks are obtained by changing the concentration of the indifferent electrolyte, these are due to the change in the cell resistance which varies with change in the concentration of the electrolyte.

FIG. 1. Effect of series resistance on the magnitude of a.c. peaks.
 1—0.004% Bromothymol blue.
 2— $4 \times 10^{-4}M$ nitrobenzene.
 3— $6 \times 10^{-4}M$ Cd^{2+} .

The magnitudes of a. c. reduction peaks of inorganic cations are concluded to be very much dependent on the dimension of the electrolysis cell and the distance between the d.m.e. and the mercury pool reference electrode, whereas organic a.c. reduction peaks and tensammetric peaks are influenced to a very small extent under similar conditions.

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